

***N*⁶-methyladenine levels in DNA increase throughout embryonic development, are enriched in the eukaryotic brain, and are a target for neurodevelopmental toxicity.**

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Abstract:

DNA methylation is one of the most important epigenetic modifications and is closely related with several biological processes such as regulation of gene transcription and the development of non-malignant diseases. The prevailing dogma states that DNA methylation in eukaryotes occurs essentially through 5-methylcytosine but recently adenine methylation was also found to be present in eukaryotes. In mouse embryonic stem cells, 6-methyladenine was associated with the repression and silencing of genes, particularly in the X-chromosome, known to play an important role in cell fate determination.

Here, we have demonstrated that 6mA is a ubiquitous eukaryotic epigenetic modification that is put in place during epigenetically sensitive periods such as embryogenesis and foetal development. In somatic cells there are clear tissue specificity in 6mA levels, with the highest 6mA levels being observed in the brain. In zebrafish, during the first 120h of embryo development, from a single pluripotent cell to an almost fully formed individual, 6mA levels steadily increase. An identical pattern was observed over embryonic days 7-21 in the mouse. Furthermore, exposure to a neurotoxic environmental pollutant during the same early life period led to a decrease in the levels of this modification.

The identification of the periods during which 6mA epigenetic marks are put in place and how they dynamically change in response to an early environmental stress, sheds a light on our understanding of mammalian epigenetic modifications and how they can trigger disease phenotypes later in life.

Introduction

Although it is known to occur in both cytosine and adenine bases, the prevailing dogma is that DNA methylation essentially occurs on the fifth position of cytosine residues. Five-methyl cytosine (5mC) is an evolutionarily conserved modification, present throughout both eukaryotes to prokaryotes, which is involved in development and afterward in the adaptation to the local environment [1-3]. Several studies from famine [4] to stressful events in life, such as war [5], suggest alterations in the deposition of this modification and its passage to the second and third generation, thereby inducing part of the heritability of certain phenotypes or disorders. Furthermore, early life adversity, such as psychosocial stress, infections or exposure to pollutants, has shown to play a major role in the development of certain disease phenotypes, and DNA methylation is believed to be the link between these events [6-10]. Exposure of rodents to Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) through the diet of the dams, such as Brominated flame retardants (e.g. hexabromocyclododecane (HBCDD) or Polycyclic aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)), during development was shown to induce significant behavioural changes (increased anxious-like behaviour, hyperactivity and altered social behaviour) in their offspring [11, 12]. These results underline the existence of a critical window of exposure for brain and behaviour development and suggest that epigenetic modifications could be involved in these behavioural impairments. Furthermore, there is growing evidence that POP exposure might be associated with the occurrence of developmental and neurodegenerative diseases (like Autism, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's), through the regulation of DNA methylation, namely 5-methylcytosine [13]. Although changes in the levels of 5mC has already been linked to POPs [10, 14], the mechanism behind exposure and later disease development is still unclear.

On the other hand, adenine methylation (6mA) has been known to be present mainly in prokaryotes since Dunn and Smith first described it in *E. Coli* in 1955 [15] and subsequently in *Aerobacter Aerogenes*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Salmonella* [16]. Since its discovery, 6mA has been associated with important biological processes in bacteria such as DNA replication, regulation of gene expression and cell defense against viruses, through the restriction-modification systems in which DNA adenine methylase (Dam) plays a role [17-20]. More recently, adenine methylation was reported in eukaryotic organisms such as plants [21], *Drosophila melanogaster* [22], *Danio rerio* [23] and mammals, such as mouse [24-26] and human [27, 28]. This is currently controversial as studies now suggest that this is due to bacterial DNA contamination in the original eukaryotic samples or that the currently available antibodies also non-specifically bind to unmethylated adenine [29-31]. Nevertheless, the enigmatic 6mA is particularly interesting in eukaryotes as the reports available so far have associated it with determining the fate of mouse embryonic stem cells, repression and silencing of genes, particularly in the X-chromosome [25] and retrotransposons [32], adaptation to

psychosocial stressors [26] and tumorigenesis [27, 28]. One common point would appear to be neuronal tissues. Levels of 6mA were increased in brain tumour biopsies when compared with normal human astrocytes [27]. Furthermore, they showed that knockdown of the demethylase ALKBH1, leads to an increase in the proliferation and tumour formation capacity. Adding to this, sequencing analysis showed that gene regions enriched in 6mA were mainly related to neuronal processes [25, 26, 28]. Other studies also reported an increased level of 6mA brain levels in specific brain areas like prefrontal cortex and amygdala in mice subjected to stress [26, 33] suggesting a high sensitivity of adenine methylation to several brain insults..

Many of the studies performed so far have relied on 6mA immunoprecipitation and sequencing (MeDIP-seq) to identify the genomic regions susceptible to methylation. A consensus is starting to emerge, focussing on 6mA in LINE-1 elements. Both Yao and Wu reported strong annotations of 6mA in LINE-1 elements in the pre-frontal cortex after stress and embryonic stem cells respectively [25, 26]. Gene ontology analysis showed that in the stress model, 6mA levels negatively correlate with neuronal gene expression and furthermore, the differentially methylated genes overlap with genes present in mental disorders such as depression and autism [26], and in the embryonic stem cell model, LINE-1 element methylation impacted their transcription as well as in their neighbouring genes [25]. This is, unfortunately contradicted by Xiao et al who observed significantly higher levels of 6mA in the mitochondria rather than on the genome *per se* (0.18% vs 0.055%) , and Koziol et al who reported 6mA in non-coding regions of the genome [34] .

The data on how adenine is modified and at what point during development or cell-type differentiation the modification is introduced are currently limited. Although the measured levels of 6mA are much lower than 5mC the available data suggests that 6mA levels increase upon fertilisation until the 64-cell stage in zebrafish and then gradually decrease as development progresses. Similarly, in the pig embryo, levels peaked at the morula stage [23]. The methylase responsible for introducing this modification in eukaryotic species such as man has been reported to be N6AMT1 [27] or METTL4 [35] (Fig. 1A), while the active demethylase has been independently reported twice as ALKBH1 or Alkbh1 in humans [27] and mice, respectively [25]. Elegant over-expression and knockout studies of both these enzymes have demonstrated that a reduction in 6mA levels promotes tumorigenesis [27], whilst increasing 6mA leads to inhibition of glioblastoma formation [28]

In this study, we evaluate the levels of 6mA in different eukaryotes species, with a special focus on mammals. Although previous studies affirm that this adenine modification is present in eukaryotes at a low density, we demonstrate that it is widely present in zebrafish, mice, rat and human, specifically in the brain. Furthermore, we report that during embryogenesis, in both zebrafish and mice, 6mA steadily increases and its global levels are significantly decreased in the cerebellum of female rats

upon exposure to organobrominated pollutants during early life. Collectively, these results may shed a light on our understanding of the mammalian epigenetic modifications and how manipulation of 6mA can help with the development of preventative or reversal strategies.

Material and Methods

Identification of 6mA from existing sequencing results

The MethSMRT database of 6mA signals in single-molecule real-time (SMRT) sequencing was interrogated [36]. MethSMRT contains single-nucleotide resolution of 6mA throughout many genomes extracted from all publicly available PacBio SMRT sequencing. For the worm (*C. elegans*), brewer's yeast (*S. cerevisiae*), thale cress (*A. thaliana*) and the fruitfly (*D. melanogaster*) the numbers of unmodified adenine residues, 6mA residues and their genomic locations were extracted. Protein sequences from man (*H. Sapiens*), Norway rat (*R. Norvegicus*), house mouse (*Mus Musculus*), zebrafish (*D. Rerio*) and the fruitfly (*D. Melanogaster*) were extracted from the NCBI under accession numbers NP_006011.2, NP_001102188.1, NP_001096035.1, NP_001018527.1 and NP_996458.1 respectively, and aligned using MUSCLE [37, 38] (European Bioinformatics Institute, UK ebi.ac.uk). Genotype-Tissue Expression data for human METLL4 and ALKBH1 enzymes described in this manuscript were downloaded from the GTEx portal on August 19th (dbGaP Accession phs000424.v8.p2, 19/08/2020).

Zebrafish embryos

Fish were housed in a ZebTec standalone recirculating tank system (Techniplast) kept at 28°C on a light:dark (14:10 hour) cycle. Fish were fed twice per day; once with granular food (Special Diet Services) and then with freshly prepared brine shrimp (*Artemia salina*). Male and female adult wild-type AB fish were mated and their offspring collected immediately following fertilization. Zebrafish embryos were dechorionated via a 5 min incubation with pronase (2mg/mL diluted in E3 medium, Roche Diagnostics GmbH, Germany) before being washed and raised in E3 medium (0.33 mM CaCl₂, 0.17 mM KCl, 5 mM NaCl, 0.33 mM MgSO₄, and 0.1% Methylene Blue, pH 7.4) as previously described [39]. To ensure sufficient genetic material for DNA extraction, zebrafish embryos were pooled at different densities across the selected time points as follows; 100 embryos were pooled immediately after fertilization (0h post fertilization), 30 embryos at 24 hpf (hours post fertilization) and 20 embryos at 48, 72 and 120 hpf. Four biological replicates were collected at each time point.

Mice embryos

Female Balb/c mice were group housed (n=5 per cage) for 10-14 days for Lee-Boot cycle synchronization and brought into oestrous by exposure to soiled bedding from a male mouse. Two females in oestrous and one male were placed in a clean "breeding" cage and left together overnight. Mating was confirmed by the presence of a vaginal plug and all animals were returned to their home cage until sacrifice. Pregnant females were sacrificed at six different time-points, from E7 to E21. The uterus was extracted and placed in PBS (4 °C) in a petri dish. Embryos were removed from the uterus,

decapitated and the brain dissected. Hippocampi and cortex were separated and stored at -20°C until further analysis.

Post mortem tissue from human brains

Human material used in this study is from a previously reported study [40]. Briefly, tissues were collected from five different donors from the region of Chang Mai, in Northern Thailand. The subjects had no underlying diseases and were hospitalized due to either car accidents, blunt chest injury or gunshot. All patients died in the Chiang Mai University Medical Hospital, where the autopsies were carried out 2-10h after the death. A 5mm punch biopsy was collected from the initial one-centimetre sections, for each of the 28 different brain regions.

Perinatal exposure to the brominated flame retardant HBCDD (HexaBromoCycloDoDecane) as an environmental early life adversity.

As previously reported [11] pregnant females Wistar dams were fed for 42 days with α -HBCDD contaminated eggs (0, 22, 66 ng/kg/day), from gestational day (GD0) onto the weaning of the offspring (PND21), constituting a solid early life adversity model in lab rats [41]. At PND270, sensory and motor impairments were evaluated by using the Locotronic apparatus (Locotronic Intelli-Bio[®], France), according to the manufacturer's instructions. The later was composed of a starting and arrival box, connected by a horizontal ladder corridor, with 3mm diameter bars (7mm spacing). Infrared sensors above and below each inter-bar space read the position, number and duration of missteps of the rat. Offspring were sacrificed at PND270. Brains were excised, flash frozen, and stored at -80°C until analysed. Serial sections (20 μ m) were mounted on Super Frost slides (Roth-Sochiel, Lauterbourg, France) and kept at -80°C until use.

DNA extraction

DNA was extracted from samples through a spin-column procedure, using the QIAamp DNA Micro Kit (56304, Qiagen), following the manufacturer's instructions. DNA quantity and quality were assessed with both nanodrop (ThermoFisher scientific) and Qubit (ThermoFisher scientific).

6mA detection by HPLC MS/MS

Prior to LC-MS/MS analysis, isolated genomic DNA was enzymatically hydrolysed to individual deoxyribonucleosides in a one-step procedure. Sample DNA (1 μ g) was supplemented with 2.5 ng [15N3]-2'-deoxycytidine (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc.) as internal standard, dried under N₂ and then hydrolyzed at 37°C, in a 10 μ l digestion mix of phosphodiesterase I (300 mU, Sigma-Aldrich, Belgium), alkaline phosphatase (200 U, Sigma-Aldrich), and BenzonaseR Nuclease (250 U,

Sigma-Aldrich),) in Tris buffer pH 7.9 (20mM Tris; Sigma), for about 8h (Godderis et al., 2015). In each sample, DNA 6-methyl-adenine was determined as previously published (Cardenas, A. et al, 2017; De Nys, S. et al., 2018; Duca et al., 2018) with minor modifications: After hydrolysis, samples were diluted with water (500 μ L), filtered using an Amicon Ultra-0.5 Centrifugal filter device (Sigma-Aldrich) and resuspended in a solution of ACN : H₂O (70:30, v/v). An aliquot of 10 μ L was injected on a hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC) column (ACQUITY UPLCR BEH Amide columns 1.7 μ m, 2.1 x 50 mm, Waters), held at a temperature of 40°C. A mixture of 1mM Ammonium Fluoride (A) and acetonitrile (B) was used as the mobile phase for chromatographic separation . A flow rate of 0.4 mL/min was applied. All HPLC solvents and reagents were from Sigma-Aldrich (LC-MS/MS grade). The analyses were carried out using a Waters Xevo TQ-XS triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Wexford, Ireland) with an electrospray ionization source (ESI) in positive mode. Multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) with an argon collision gas was used to improve quantification, selectivity and sensitivity. MS/MS parameters for the specific detection by MRM are detailed in Table 1. The peaks were identified as previously described [42]. Samples have been analysed in a random manner and without prior identification of the different treatment groups.

Dot blot

DNA (100 μ g) was denaturated at 95°C for 10 min, flash-cooled on ice and neutralised with 10% (v/v) of 6.6M Ammonium Acetate. Samples were spotted on a nylon membrane (GE Healthcare, Whatman Nytran SuperCharge), air-dried for 10 min and UV-crosslinked for 90 seconds (Ingenius syngene bio imaging). Membranes were then blocked (5% non-fat milk, 1% BSA in 0.1% PBST) for 1h at room temperature (RT) followed by incubation with the primary anti-N⁶-methyladenine antibody (Synaptic Systems) diluted 1:1000 in blocking solution overnight, at 4°C. After washing 3 times with 0.1% PBST, membranes were incubated with anti-rabbit IgG antibody (Thermofisher scientific) diluted 1:5000 in blocking solution for 2h at RT. Signal was detected (Intas ECL Chemocam Imager) after 5 min incubation with ECL Plus Western Blotting Substrate (Pierce) following the manufacturers' recommendations. Signal intensity was quantified with ImageJ software [43].

Immunohistochemistry

6mA:After temperature equilibration (10 min, RT) slides with cerebellum sections from 2 male and 2 female individuals were rinsed with PBS 1x for 5 min, and underwent rehydration and permeabilisation (PBS1X, Triton-X 0.3%), for 10 min, followed by antigen retrieval (2M HCl) for 45 min and neutralisation (0.1M Tris-HCl) for 20 min. Non-specific binding was blocked (PBS1x, BSA 1%, Triton-X 0.3%, RNase A 50 μ g/mL) for 1h. After blocking, slides were washed with 1X PBS (3 x 5 min) and incubated with primary antibody (1:500, rabbit-anti-6mA, Synaptic Systems) for 1h (RT). After

washing (3x 5 minutes, 1x PBS) a 1:2000 Alexa Fluor 488-anti-rabbit IgG (ab150077, Abcam) was used for visualisation. Finally, the slides were washed with 1X PBS (3x 5 minutes) and mounted with anti-fade mounting medium which contained DAPI (Thermo Fisher, Belgium).

Cytochrome c oxidase : Cerebellum sections were incubated with a cytochrome substrate buffer (100 mg DAB-4HCl (Sigma, France), 40 mg cytochrome c (Sigma, France), 36 g catalase (Sigma, France) in 0.1 M Phosphate buffer, pH 7.4) for 65 minutes at 37°C, in the dark and with agitation as described in Crepeaux et al. [12]) The reaction was stopped by washing the sections for 5 minutes with cold 0.1 M Phosphate buffer containing 10% sucrose, sections were fixed in 4% formaldehyde for 30 min and washed three times with 0.1 M Phosphate buffer (5 min each). Sections were dehydrated ascending ethanol baths (50, 70, 96, 100%) for 3 min, cleared with toluene twice for 5 min and mounted (Eukitt mounting medium, Sigma, France). Stained sections were analysed using BIOCOM system (Les Ulis, France), using the standard curve to calculate $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{g}$ of tissue from optical density.

Statistical analysis

All results were expressed as mean \pm SEM. For each group, a Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality of the distributions as well as a Bartlett test for equality of variances were performed. When normality of the distribution and homogeneity of variance were assumed, a two-way ANOVA test was performed to compare different groups, followed by a post hoc Bonferroni test. Locotronic activity was analysed using non-parametric procedures (Kruskal-Wallis test for comparison among the 3 groups at the 1st and the 2nd trials, Wilcoxon procedure to compare performances between the two trials in each group). Statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS 16.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) or GraphPad Prism version 8.0.0 for Windows (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California USA). Heatmaps were generated in R v3.5.3.

Table 1- MS/MS parameters for MRM detection of modified and unmodified hydrolysed nucleosides.

Compounds Cone	Ionization mode	Transitions (m/z)	Collision energy (eV)	Cone (V)
[15N3]-2'- deoxycytidine (IS)	ESI+	231 \rightarrow 115	15	12
2'-deoxyadenine	ESI+	268 \rightarrow 135	18	26
	ESI+	268 \rightarrow 119	42	26

N⁶-methyl-2'- deoxyadenine	ESI+	282 → 149	14	2
	ESI+	282 → 133	40	2

Results

6-mA as a genuine eukaryotic modification

As the literature casts doubt on the existence of 6mA in eukaryotic DNA, we searched the MethSMRT database for direct 6mA reads from PacBio SMRT sequencing data. Direct reading of 6mA from the SMRT data ensures that the DNA from the target species is genomic DNA and does not represent contamination from bacterial, viral or mitochondrial DNA. 6-mA levels in three different species, *Drosophila melanogaster*, *Caenorhabditis elegans* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Fig. 1B) are in accordance with the literature, ranging from 1.25% to 1.75% of the total existent Adenines, representing 200,000 to 290,000 adenines in each of the genomes (Fig. 1C). This modification appears to be more abundant in Exons and Promoter regions. Furthermore, homologues of two key enzymes in the methylation / demethylation machinery were identified in *H. sapiens*, as well as *D. rerio*, *M. musculus* and *R. norvegicus* (Fig. 1F). ALKBH1 was also present in *D. melanogaster* (Fig. 1D). METTL4 is a conserved methyltransferase, while ALKBH1 is a conserved demethylase. The sequences of these were highly conserved with an average 71% homology (range 42-92%, Fig. 1E, G). Available RNA Seq data from the GENx and Illumina human body map v2.0 suggests that both enzymes are expressed throughout the human body and that levels are uniform, suggesting that a defined level is required in all tissue of the body (Fig. 2A and 2B).

6-methyladenine detection and quantification

We established 6mA detection using two independent techniques. Initially we established a LC-MS/MS detection of 6mA with increased selectivity since in addition to compound identification with retention time, we were also able to confirm its presence with MRM (multiple reaction monitoring) transitions. The analytical method is detailed in Table 1. Furthermore, an extra confirmation transition was used to ensure the presence of each target compound. To confirm the later, the ratio “quantification transition to confirmation transition” was determined as the difference from the ratio obtained with standard compounds below 20%. Based on previous literature reports, we also measured 6mA using dot blot with a specific antibody against 6-methyladenine (6mA). This technique allowed us to measure the levels of this modification through quantification of the signal intensity of the DNA dots spotted on a membrane given by the oxidation of the luminol present in the revealing agent.

The linearity of detection between the dot blot and LC MS/MS techniques was then evaluated to validate the presence of 6mA in eukaryotic DNA (Fig. 3A). DNA samples, isolated from cerebellum collected from both female and male rats exposed or not to HBCDD at 22 and 66 ng/kg/day, was subjected to both types of analysis. Fig. 3A displays a linear correlation between the two sets of data

(Spearman analysis, $n = 26$, $r^2 = 0.81$, $p < 0.001$) confirming the suitability of these two methods to produce comparable results. Based on this, all further 6mA results presented in this study are based on dot blot analysis.

Finally, by using immunocytochemistry, we visualized for the first time the presence of 6mA in the cerebellar cells of rats (PND270) exposed or not through the dam to α -HBCDD at 66 ng/kg/day. Methylation of adenine is shown to be nicely located in the nucleus of cerebellar cells (Fig 3B). As only two individuals/sex/group were taken to generate the present images, no quantification of the signal was done.

6-methyladenine presence in mammals

Having convinced ourselves that 6mA was a genuine eukaryotic epigenetic modification that we could detect, we determined its body-wide tissue distribution in a model species, the mouse, and performed a detailed examination in the most relevant human tissue. DNA from nine different adult mice organs, from the cardiovascular to the neuronal and digestive system, was examined by dot blot for 6mA. This modification was detected in all organs and its abundance, unlike the classical 5mC, was not equally distributed throughout the tissues. The highest abundance was in the lung, spleen and brain, represented by prefrontal cortex (PFC), (Fig. 4A) that were 1.8, 1.7 and 1.9 times more abundant than the weakest tissue: the heart. The higher levels in the brain appears to agree with the GTEx RNA-Seq data that suggests lower expression of the demethylase enzymes in the brain. As such, we performed a detailed examination of 6mA presence in twenty-eight different human brain regions from five human donors. Additionally, data from the human brains confirm this abundance where tissue specificity also seems to play a role with white matter being the most methylated tissue, having 3.9 times higher levels of 6mA than the weakest tissue: the Superior occipital gyrus (SOG) (Fig. 4B). The amygdala is the second brain region with higher methylation levels, having almost 3 times more methylated adenines than the SOG. This is a region involved in fear conditioning and known to be susceptible to stressful events and, together with our previous findings, these observations consolidate the fact that 6mA may play a role in the response to stress.

Embryonic states of both mice and zebrafish show a linear increase in the levels of 6mA

Mice and zebrafish embryos were collected at different time points, in order to cover the whole gestational period, a critical period in the foetal development. Contrarily to 5mC, dynamic changes throughout early and late development, adenine modifications seem to steadily increase as the embryo develops from a single pluripotent cell to an almost fully formed individual consisting of mainly somatic cells, both in zebrafish and mice (Fig. 5A and 5B). In mice, from day 7 to a fully formed embryo the amount of 6mA significantly increases 3.5 times ($***p < 0.001$) and the same trend can

be observed throughout the pregnancy with significant increases of 1.8 times from day 11 to 16 (* $p < 0.05$) and 1.6 times from day 14 to 16 (* $p = 0.01$) (Fig. 5A). In zebrafish, the same behaviour is observed and although is not significantly increasing during the development process, the values of 6mA suffer a 38 fold increase from fertilization to fully formed embryo (* $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 5B). These observations suggest that 6mA may play an important role in the development and can help us understand how a deviation from normal development can trigger the disease phenotypes such as neurodevelopmental disorders later in life.

Early life exposure to α -HBCDD induces change in 6mA levels in F1 generation at PND270

After exploring the linearity between LC-MS/MS and immunoblotting techniques, we decided to evaluate how values of 6mA change in the brain of rats followed an early life adversity induced by an exposure to α -HBCDD through the dams. This BFR known to be present in indoor environment, food products like eggs and poultry meat and human daily basis has recently been classified as “substance of high concern” at the European level [44, 45]. Exposure to such contaminant could constitute a risk for vulnerable individuals such as foetuses and new-borns, due to its proved toxicity for the endocrine system and for neurodevelopment. At PND270, the statistical analysis of 6mA in cerebellum showed a tendency in the interaction between the sex and the treatment ($p = 0.079$) related to the decrease in 6mA observed at the dose 22 mg/kg/kg ($p = 0.079$). Female rats subjected to α -HBCDD treatment was 0.81 times lower when compared to the control group (Fig. 6A). This observation confirms that early life is a critical period and that environmental changes such as exposure to pollutants can have impact the epigenome. Similarly, cytochrome oxidase activity measured in the interposed nuclei showed a significant interaction between the sex and the treatment related to the same CO decrease at the dose 22 mg/kg/kg ($p < 0.05$) as observed for 6mA. Female rats subjected to α -HBCDD treatment was 0.80 times lower when compared to the control group (Fig. 6B).

To see if these changes in 6mA levels in cerebellar cells and CO activity in the interposed nuclei observed in female rats may result in behavioural impairments, motor coordination and learning capacity were evaluated in the Locotronic apparatus. In the first trial, variations in the time spent to perform the test and the number of leg errors were observed in animals exposed to HBCDD 22 ng/kg/d compared to controls and HBCDD-66 groups, but this tends to be significant only for leg errors ($p = 0.095$, KW test). The same kind of variation was observed in the second trial but it was not significant ($p = 0.125$, KW test). Comparisons between the two trials in each group showed a significant reduction (or tendency) in both variables in the 3 groups. These results suggest that a perinatal exposure at α -HBCDD at 22 mg/kg/day could induce a deficit of coordination in adult female rats while the learning abilities of the animals to correct this deficit remain unaffected by the exposure to HBCDD.

Discussion

Epigenetic modifications are known to occur in RNA, DNA and histones and, although they may change the accessibility of the DNA region and/or gene expression, the original DNA sequence remains unaltered [46]. To date, 5mC was the *ex-libris* of DNA methylation in eukaryotes. Only recently, 6mA, originally described in prokaryotes [15, 16], has been found in eukaryotes and proved to have functional roles [25, 26, 28, 47]. In this study we demonstrate not only that in our laboratory 6mA is a genuine eukaryotic DNA modification, but also that it is widely distributed throughout rodents' tissues, with major enrichment in the brain, as recently described [26]. Furthermore, in a neurodevelopmental toxicity model, 6mA levels were strongly influenced by perinatal exposure to the pollutant HBCDD and associated with the behavioural anomalies seen upto 8 months after exposure.

There is currently some uncertainty in the literature as to whether 6mA is a genuine eukaryotic DNA modification [29, 30, 48]. Initially, we confirmed that the methylation machinery is common to many eukaryotic species and that the available 3rd generation sequencing datasets provide direct-read evidence for the modification being found in regions of identifiable eukaryotic DNA. As potential sources of contamination have previously been reported, we removed the zebrafish chorion prior to DNA extraction, reducing the contamination from bacterial DNA, and as such, the 6mA levels represents that in the uncontaminated zebrafish gDNA [30]. Similarly, mouse embryos were extracted from the sterile in-utero environment, reducing the risk of bacterial contamination. We extracted the genomic locations of 6mA from the MethSMRT database. This is an extraction of 6mA calls from direct long reads from PacBio Sequencing, with base-calling that identifies 6mA from the original read. This also excludes the hypothesis that 6mA calls are a contaminant as the surrounding eukaryotic sequence is read, confirming the species of origin of 6mA. Furthermore, we demonstrated the concordance of the results of 6mA measurement by two methods (dot blot and LC-MS/MS), which leads us to believe that these two independent techniques are robust enough to allow the detection and quantification of 6mA. Moreover, we were able to show, for the first time, that like 5mC, 6mA is present in tissues from all the major eukaryotic organ systems in mice, specifically in the digestive, cardiovascular and immune system. We also provide the first evidence of the presence of 6mA in twenty-eight different human brain regions. Interestingly, the brain region where we measured the higher levels of methylated adenine was the white matter, shown and described to take a great part on the development of the brain tumours [49, 50]. These results, together with the RNA sequencing results illustrating the lower levels of the demethylases expression in the human brain, are in line with the recently described high levels of 6mA in Glioblastoma cell lines [28] and may help to elucidate the mechanisms behind such events. Furthermore, the role of the conserved methyltransferase, and demethylase in the folate cycle and DNA methylation warrants further biochemical investigation.

Increasing evidence highlights that chronic stress, particularly in early life, could interfere and regulate the levels of DNA methylation, which, in turn, acts on the expression of certain genes [51-53]. Our results from animals exposed to α -HBCDD during early life are consistent with alterations in DNA methylation, with decreased levels of 6mA in the cerebellum, revealing the importance of this modification in the processes initiated by stress.

Earlier studies detected the accumulation of 6mA during embryogenesis, in genomic DNA from sperm, oocytes and several embryonic stages of pig and zebrafish [23]. Considering our previous results and the knowledge from embryogenesis, we decided to investigate the behaviour of 6mA during the whole gestation period of zebrafish and mice. Our data from zebrafish embryos confirms the accumulation of methylated adenines during this period and, contrarily to what was previously published by Liu et al. we demonstrate that this modification steadily increases until birth. Recent data confirms this increase during development [32]. The levels of 6mA in the hippocampus of mice embryos provided similar results to the zebrafish, encouraging the hypothesis that 6mA has a role in neurogenesis. Opposite of what it happens with 5mC that changes dynamically throughout embryogenesis [54], 6mA appears to significantly change its levels from early embryonic days up to the very end of pregnancy. DNA methylation, namely 5mC or 5hmC, has already been proven to play an important role in neurodevelopment [55-57] and deviations to a normal pregnancy, in various forms, lead to neurodevelopmental disorders [58-60]. The physiological role of 6mA appears to be in the silencing of both genes and transposons such as at long interspersed element 1 (LINE-1) [32]. Although LINE-1 retrotransposons make up around 17% of the human genome, they are highly mobile, and cause somatic mosaicism that has been linked to both neurodevelopmental disorders and psychiatric disorders such as Schizophrenia [61, 62].

One of our key observations is that 6mA levels increase throughout embryogenesis. This suggests that this modification is introduced as the foetus differentiates and fully differentiated somatic cells accumulate. As such, the role of 6mA in the developmental origins of health and disease is obvious. Given the developmental role that is becoming apparent in the literature, we have expanded this. Not only have we shown that 6mA can be found in all tissues, and confirmed the fact that it is enriched in the brain, we have been able to study variations in 6mA brain levels by the administration of α -HBCDD, an organobrominated flame retardant of high concern, during a crucial neurodevelopmental period. Changes in 6mA level in cerebellum were measured at PND270 in a model that was shown to concurrently induce neurobehavioral deficiencies. The neurodevelopmental toxicity of α -HBCDD has been recently studied by evaluating neurobehavioural impairments induced by α -HBCDD exposure via the food during the gestation

and lactation in dam rats at concentration levels which were representative of human exposure (22 and 66 ng/kg bw/day) [11, 41], showing some short- and long-term behavioural impairments observed only in rats exposed to the lowest dose 22 ng/kg/day [11]. These results are consistent with alterations observed in animals exposed at the same level of dose at PND270 in i) DNA methylation, (decreased levels of 6mA in the cerebellum), ii) in CO activity (decreased activity in the interposed nuclei) and iii) in locomotor coordination observed in female exposed at 22 ng/kg/day of HBCDD at PND270. Taken together, these results pointed out the potential role of this epigenetic modification in the processes initiated by α -HBCDD exposure. Further investigations need therefore to be carried out to confirm if early life exposures to α -HBCDD may induce 6mA epigenetic hallmarks in the developing brain, which in turn may affect behaviour of the offspring at adulthood.

While it is clear that further studies are required in order to better understand the role and plasticity of 6mA in development and pathophysiological processes, our findings provide important links between 6-methyladenine, neurogenesis, and changes in behaviour as well as inflammation in the adult brain.

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Conflict of interest: The authors all declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethics statement: All animals used in this study were maintained in accordance with all current European Union (Directive 2010/63/EU), national and local ethical guidelines and legal regulations. Mouse and zebrafish embryo experiments were performed in accordance with the LIH institutional animal welfare structure requirements as well as the European Union Directive 2010/63/EU as implemented in national legislation. Rat experiments were approved and supervised by the institutional ethics committee of the University of Lorraine (authorization number B54-547-13).

Figure Legends

Figure 1: 6mA is a conserved eukaryotic epigenetic modification with conserved epigenetic machinery. (A) Schematic representation of the current knowledge of 6mA. As for 5mC, the methyl group is donated by S-Adenosyl methionine (SAM), leaving S-Adenosyl homocysteine (SAH). Reported methyl transferases include..... Demethylases include..... (B) Relative abundance and (C) absolute abundance of direct-read 6mA calls from 3 eukaryotic species extracted from the MethSMART database of direct calls from PacBio sequencing, with identifiable eukaryotic sequence surrounding the methylation call. (D) Hierarchical clustering of sequence alignment and (E) percentage sequence homology for the demethylase ALKBH1. (F) Hierarchical clustering of sequence alignment and (G) percentage sequence homology for the methyltransferase METTL4.

Figure 2: Genotype-Tissue Expression data for (A) human METLL4 methyltransferase and (B) ALKBH1 demethylase. Data were downloaded from the GTEX portal on August 19th, (dbGaP Accession phs000424.v8.p2, 19/08/2020).

Figure 3: (A) Representation of the linearity between the dot blot and LC-MS/Ms techniques. (linear relationship was evaluated by Spearman analysis, $n = 26$, $r^2 = 0.81$, $p < 0.001$); (B) Immunofluorescence 6mA detection in cerebellum of female and males rat exposed through the dams to α -HBCDD at PND270. DAPI in blue, primary AB anti-6mA (1:500), secondary AB AF488 in red (1:2000), 20x objective. To represent the α -HBCDD and control group, two males and 2 females were taken out of each group to perform this protocol and generate representative pictures.

Figure 4: Quantification of the distribution of 6mA throughout the different tissues in (A) mice and in (B) different human brain regions (B) via dot blot. Data are from 4 biological replicates in mice and 5 in humans, and presented as mean +/- SEM.

Figure 5: Quantification of 6mA modification in genomic DNA extracted from (A) zebrafish (A) and (B) mice, at different developmental stages. Later embryonic stages show a higher accumulation of this modification when comparing to the early stages. . Data are from 20-100 biological replicates for zebrafish and 5 to 8 for mice, and presented as mean +/- SEM.

Figure 6: HBCDD alters 6mA levels in the cerebellum and motricity. (A) 6mA Dot blot quantification of 6mA in the cerebellum at PND270. Females represented in red, males in blue. (B) cytochrome oxidase activity measurement in the interposed at PND270. Females represented in red, males in blue. (C) and (D) Evaluation of Motor coordination and learning capacity of the female rats at PND270 by the comparison of the time spent in the apparatus and the number of leg errors between two trials. Comparisons between the 2 trials were carried out by using Wilcoxon test for multiple comparisons.

Comparisons between the 3 groups were performed by using Kruskal Wallis test for multiple comparisons. In (C) Blue and green bars represent the time spent to perform the first and second trial, respectively. and in (D) the number of missteps in the first and second trial, respectively.

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